

A NOTE WHY ADDED MASS CONCEPT IS MATHEMATICALLY NEEDED

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ABSTRACT

One of the resistance to the added mass adaption is the idea that solution of the Navier–Stokes equations provides the solution. Several physical expansions have been provided in the past as why the added mass has be added and why the NS solution is not the total solution of the problem. It could be that the arguments in these explanations which are based on the physics not sufficient to convince the detractors. This paper is an attempt to offer a different view for which emphasizes the mathematical lens and prospective and thus convincing others in the essential of the added mass. Perhaps this mathematical observation could be used in other situations with similar underline problems.

The physics is typically described by some mathematical models which contain some kind of differential equation(s). The cases where integral equation(s) described the situations are somewhat different and a modified approach is needed. Differential equations require boundary and or initial conditions with one degree less or much less. For example, the second order ODE allows only for derivative or the function or combination of both (no second order derivative on the boundary). The concept of the added mass stems from the mathematical point of view ability or need to impose the same order boundary conditions as the equation(s) (when conditions are linear or elliptic).

Key Words

Added Mass, Boundary Conditions, Higher Order Boundary conditions

1 Introduction

The majority of the engineers, physicists, and mathematicians do not aware of the added mass concept because it is not introduced

in undergraduate or graduate study in most places (this statement is given without a reference or proof). Perhaps the only engineering discipline that it is mandatory is the marine engineering (under different names) and some unique programs. Yet this paper examines when the added mass should be included in the calculations and when it is not relevant. For example, over 300 teams from all around world try to solve the critical plunger velocity in die casting with budget of millions of dollars (Bar-Meir and Brauner 2021). By the way, they attempted solve the problem using approach which requires them to consider the added mass and yet all teams ignore the added mass. This article focuses on the mathematical aspects and none on the die casting itself and hence while introduced this problem it discuss the added mass idea on background of the die casting critical plunger velocity.

This article intended exclusively to be persuasive, yet even though some elements can be extended to other mathematical/physical problems. This example will be discussed to illuminate the concept why the added mass is important. Consider a typical second order differential equation of the form

$$\frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Clearly, second derivative cannot prescribe as a condition either as initial condition or the boundary. In this discussion, it is assumed that the derivatives are a full integers, that is dy/dx and not say $d^{0.99}y/dx^{0.99}$. The factional derivative are a class of its own and it is not discussed here¹. In this specific case, the bound-

¹Please do not ask this author questions about these terrible creatures. It was not a pleasant time dealing with those and when this author realizes that he can be complete idiot.

ary condition can be of form of $c = f(dy/dx, y)$. Thus, what happens when the boundary has to describe second order derivative or effect? Currently in mathematical circles, the second derivative as boundary condition is dismissed as impossibility. This issue is the core issue from the mathematical point of view of the idea of the added mass.

The die casting process provides an excellent example to demonstrate this point. A plunger (piston without getting to the semantics difference between the two terms) pushes liquid metal into a cavity (mold). The flow in the shot sleeve (in die casting terminology for cylinder) for this discussion is assumed to be one dimensional. While completely wrong, it is assumed the piston pushes liquid metal in the cavity which is full. The difference between this situation and regular (internal combustion engine) piston cylinder system is that the relative density of the liquid metal (vs density of gas) is very high. The piston is pushing air/gases and does not have a large added mass. In die casting it is the opposite. Supposed that the governing equation is one dimensional Navier–Stokes equation, when at least most people will agree, if the 2D and 3D effects can be neglected. The only problem is the boundary conditions which many assume to be no–slip condition which at minimum creates a singular point at the connection of the piston and cylinder (one requires zero and one requires the piston velocity). Even though this boundary condition is wrong, but for the discussion here it is assumed to be correct. The governing equation reads in this case as

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial U_x}{\partial t} + U_x \frac{\partial U_x}{\partial x} \right) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_x}{\partial x^2} \right) + \rho g_x \quad (2)$$

This equation is taken from (Bar-Meir 2023; Bar-Meir 2021). One of the solution suggested by the these teams was no slip at the plunger (piston) tip. Thus, the solution is based on the boundary conditions where the tip is at specified the locations of the plunger with respect to the time. Thus, the calculations or solution is based these proposed boundary conditions, the acceleration of liquid metal is not accounted for. Yet, most people intuition is that if the piston accelerated so must the liquid metal. This point is where the needed force for the plunger has to be supplemented by the added mass to accounted for the liquid metal acceleration.

Maybe the plunger force required for the acceleration can be assumed to be the accelerated liquid metal plus plunger weight plus the whole liquid metal. On physical ground this assumption is wrong because the directions the liquid metal sequments and the change and resistance etc. In that case, the added mass concept has to be employed. While the calculations of the added mass are not simple and they are not provided here, they should

be used.

The Navier–Stokes equations can be converted to Euler equations when the viscosity switch to be zero and hence the added mass can be calculated, maybe. However, Navier–Stokes equations when solved for non zero viscosity, the acceleration (second derivative) is not accounted for. It does not factored into the calculations. From physical point of view, the explanation is bit different and it seems intuitive for example see for example von Karman using the added mass for landing air plane (1929) where the energy transfer to the added mass. While von Karman did not even use the term added mass (this author have seemed even a single case where von Karman use the term added mass), yet, he got the correct energy transfer mechanism.

When the added mass must or should be used? The added mass should be used in cases where the relative density is large and there is acceleration with interaction of the solid–liquid interface. For example, when impeller is analyzed the added mass should be considered. Yet for example, a random section of a paper on this topic like Le et al (2023) show ignoring the added mass. While ignoring the many remarks that should be made on that paper, clearly the added mass has impact the results but it was ignored.

Here is a small sample of ingnoring the added mass in the marine: Bianchi (2022) studied the Cownose Ray where is simply disregarded the added mass. In recent example is Zeng (2023). When the author asked about it, he stated “[t]he CFD directly solves the Navier–Stokes equations and the added mass is not needed in this model”. Yet, even as recently several textbooks on ship stability even standard fluid mechanics deny the existence of added mass (see GATE famous Indian test).

Concluding Remarks

In this paper it was show anohter argument for the use of the added mass. While the physical arguments are legitimate and correct this discussion is offered as another avenue to the acceptance of the added mass and when it should be used. Perhaps this idea of imposing an effect of the same order the ODE can be used in other cases.

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About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made and on how many

people plagiarized his work. In fact, this author proud of the rejections of his papers by the establishment where his papers were rejected on the ground of not enough academic merit or other nonesese only to reach millions of readers and to find alternative motives to their rejections. Recently, actions of the arXiv.org by individual hiding behide the title monitor to suggeted these claims. Likley these days this kind of action does not work.

In the die casting industry, this author has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions of dollars promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing these discoveries. The irony is that these author's models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, this servant solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation).

Kostas J. Spyrou, when he gave his keynote lecture, basically copied many concepts that were developed by Bar-Meir (such as the stability dome) and presented them as his ideas. These concepts had never appeared any the literature before. It is interesting to point out that Dr. Spyrou has been observed downloading Bar-Meir's book. Dr. Spyrou's behavior is not unique to him only. Dr. Kenneth Brezinsky went out of his way to declare that Bar-Meir's calculations of compressible gas potential were useless and baseless. However, Brian J. Cantwell from Stanford University recently decided to plagiarize Bar-Meir's idea and to dedicate a whole section (2.9) to this topic in his book (and probably also in his classes). Except that Dr. Cantwell oversimplified the idea (he removed the dimensionless presentation), maybe because he did not fully understand it. The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to the discoveries of this author.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar-Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert

testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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